

Challenges in the Implementation of DSWD Educational Assistance Program as Basis for Enhancement

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Abstract

This study identified the challenges faced by recipients and implementers of the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) educational assistance program, providing a basis for enhancing program efficiency in terms of processing requirements and distribution of assistance. The findings revealed no significant differences in the challenges encountered by recipients based on the name of school, type of school, or type of student. Similarly, no significant differences were observed among implementers regarding the challenges of processing requirements and distribution, irrespective of their years of service, licensure status, or professional designation. However, the qualitative analysis revealed key themes that highlight areas for improvement. Among recipients, three themes emerged: Organizational Process (41.10%), Participation of Recipients (10.96%), and Information Dissemination (5.48%). Among implementers, 75% of respondents emphasized the need for improved Cooperation of Recipients. In comparison, 12.5% identified the Enhancement of Manpower as a critical factor. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research designs, as well as correlational and descriptive-comparative analyses, to delineate the challenges faced by both groups. A purposive sampling technique was used, involving 116 college students and 8 program implementers in Nueva Vizcaya. This research is significant as it provides evidence-based insights into the operational inefficiencies of the DSWD educational assistance program. By addressing the challenges identified, the study offers practical recommendations for improving program implementation, ultimately ensuring more equitable and effective support for students in need. This can contribute to the overall success of educational assistance programs and reinforce their role in fostering academic achievement and social development.

Keywords: *DSWD, education, program implementers, recipient*

Introduction

The conceptualization of social assistance finds its origins in the principles set forth by the United Nations (UN), an international body established in 1945 with the participation of 193 member states, aimed at addressing the dynamic global landscape. In pursuit of this objective, the UN embraced the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, outlining 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to be achieved by member states by the year 2030 (Montiel et al., 2021). Underscoring the vital role of education, the United Nations acknowledges its significance in advancing diverse Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as observed by Adipat and Chotikapanich (2022). Their findings highlight that a quality education possesses transformative potential, contributing to societal stability, enhancing access to opportunities, and nurturing tolerance. Accordingly, this is the focus of the educational assistance program set by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) through the Crisis Intervention Section. From the first-semester assessment report of the DSWD for the year 2023, the educational assistance served a total of 9,424 recipients (DSWD, 2023).

However, acquiring a good quality of education to carry off the said vision of the SDG in education through the DSWD educational assistance is hindered by many disadvantages. The impetus behind the establishment of social services or social assistance in diverse nations is rooted in the recognition that socio-economic disadvantage hampers individuals' ability to meet fundamental needs, thereby hindering life improvement. This has led to the inception of social assistance programs worldwide to confront a spectrum of societal challenges. Shahidi et al. (2019)

posit that one crucial mechanism employed by governments to mitigate the repercussions of socio-economic disparities is the provision of social assistance, with a pronounced focus on the educational domain.

Within the framework of social assistance, attention to the educational sector is often articulated as "Educational Assistance." Broadly construed, educational assistance encompasses various forms of in-kind or cash transfers dedicated to educational purposes.

Access to proper education stands as a fundamental necessity, serving as a foundational step for individual survival in a world that continually evolves with heightened demands for sustaining and advancing life. Furthermore, the impact of education extends beyond individual development, contributing to transformative changes at both micro and macro levels. In the Philippines, a strong belief in the significance of education is deeply ingrained in the Filipino culture, where it is regarded as a vital legacy passed down from generation to generation (Cereño & Pogoy, 2020). Recognizing these challenges, educational assistance programs emerge as social services, aiming to provide additional support to students, addressing specific educational expenses they struggle to meet. A Co-initiated research conducted by the DSWD in 2018 revealed that educational assistance in the Philippines was able to achieve a minimum standard in its implementation with AICS by requiring the requirements and executing major processes. However, in the reality of the implementation, adjustments to the existing guidelines may occur which can be grounded by the decisions of related stakeholders in the different areas such as additional requirements and processes (DSWD, 2018). Additionally, these changes are utilized to supplement the lack of resources or weaknesses of the program, which usually limits eligible clients to apply and client satisfaction.

Over slightly more than two decades, the allocated budget for educational assistance has consistently constituted the largest proportion of the overall government expenditure earmarked for targeted social initiatives. This financial commitment has consistently surpassed allocations for health, village, and community programs, as documented by Yusuf and Sumner in 2015. In the Philippines, Murillo (2023) reports that the DSWD Educational Assistance Program is implemented through the Assistance to Individuals in Crisis Situations which is a mandate from the DSWD Memorandum Circular No. 02, series of 2014 entitled Guidelines to Strengthen and Enhance the Implementation of the Assistance to Individuals in Crisis Situations (AICS), specifically designed to offer financial support to students from low-income families. This supplemental grant aims to alleviate various educational expenses, including tuition fees, miscellaneous school fees, and the cost of school supplies. Eligible individuals qualifying for this program can receive a cash grant to cover their educational costs, with the amount varying based on the student's level of education. According to the DSWD 2024 requirements, up to three students per indigent family can receive aid ranging from Php 1,000 for elementary students, Php 2,000 for high school students, Php 3,000 for senior high school students, and Php 4,000 for tertiary students. The program's benefits encompass financial assistance for various school-related expenses, such as tuition fees, books, and other necessary materials. Notably, the assistance is not restricted to college students but extends to all levels of education, from elementary to high school and even vocational/technical schools.

The pursuit of a high-quality education is deemed a valuable aspect of life, fostering intellectual development and providing avenues for seizing opportunities to meet life's demands. Zhan et al. (2022) assert that educational attainment significantly contributes to improving the quality of life in both the short and long term. However, Bernardo and Resureccion (2018) point out that education also presents challenges, particularly in the form of financial constraints. The DSWD as a government agency which aims to secure its people was actively maneuvered to assist students seeking for educational assistance through the Assistance to Individual in Crisis Situations from different field offices (Quimoyog, 2022).

In the Philippines, the most recent issue of the DSWD educational assistance highlighted its unorganized distribution as reported by Alcaraz during the first semester of the post-pandemic academic year (2022). In connection with this, further issues included the cancellation of scheduled payouts in other places such as Western Visayas due to a lack of funds as reported by Lena (2022). The involvement of the assigned program implementers who maneuver the program during its implementation are also targeted with commentaries and put into question whenever such issues arise. Sullivan et al. (2018), pointed out that challenges that disrupt the implementation of services and programs include human resources and staffing issues, infrastructure, resources allocation and geography, referrals and marketing, leadership support, and team dynamics and processes.

The Philippines places a high value on education, spanning primary, secondary, and tertiary levels, with a notable focus on challenges within educational assistance programs, particularly affecting those enrolled in tertiary education. Baltimore and Washington (2021) of the University Professional and Continuing Education Association (UPCEA) revealed that about two in five college (42%) students discontinue their studies due to financial constraints, among another percentage of students who are most likely to discontinue college due to family commitments: 32% and health reasons: 15%.

The financial situation of students significantly impacts their academic performance, with insufficient financial support identified as a barrier to academic improvement (Dang & Bulus, 2015). Despite numerous studies exploring the implementation of the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) educational assistance, a research gap exists regarding the challenges faced by recipients and program implementers. Existing studies predominantly evaluate program effectiveness, leaving unexplored the challenges experienced both by recipients and implementers that could inform program enhancement. While overall satisfaction with educational programs is reported as high, considering further measures are still needed for improvements (Reyes et al., 2021).

The study posits that a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by recipients and implementers is crucial for both the DSWD and their human resources, providing a basis for program enhancement. Furthermore, the findings of this study are anticipated to be valuable for future researchers seeking to enhance programs and services, as well as for other service providers developing new educational assistance initiatives. Additionally, social workers currently engaged in providing services and those planning to implement similar programs could benefit from the insights derived from this study.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to identify the challenges of the recipients and implementers of DSWD educational assistance as a basis for program enhancement and specifically answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of?
 - a. Recipient
 - Name of School
 - Type of school (Public or Private)
 - Type of Student (Working or Non-working)
 - b. Implementer
 - Number of years in service
 - Type of Implementer

2. What is the level of difficulty experienced in the implementation of DSWD educational assistance in terms of?
 - a. Processing the program requirements
 - b. Distribution of educational assistance
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of difficulty experienced in the implementation of DSWD educational assistance programs when grouped according to their profile?
4. What are the challenges faced by the recipients and the implementers of DSWD educational assistance in terms of?
 - a. Processing the program requirements
 - b. Distribution of educational assistance
5. What are recommendations to solve the challenges in the implementation of the DSWD educational assistance program?

Statement of the Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the level of difficulty experienced in the implementation of the DSWD educational assistance program when grouped according to their profile.

Methodology

This research study was conducted in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, the center of education in the province with three institutions offering the tertiary level of education specifically Nueva Vizcaya State University, PLT College Inc., and Saint Mary's University. Additionally, the Department of Social Welfare and Development (SWAD) is located at Bayombong where the implementer of the DSWD educational assistance program works consisting of a total of 11 implementers. The researchers implemented a correlational and descriptive-comparative research design to precisely delineate distinctions between the challenges experienced by recipients and the program implementer of the DSWD educational assistance, thereby providing a basis for improvement. The quantitative facet of the design is focused on numerical analysis, encompassing the calculation of the total responses to survey questions.

A purposive sampling technique was utilized in selecting the respondents for the survey questionnaire wherein 73 total recipients participated out of 116 recipients of the DSWD educational assistance program in A.Y. 2023-2024. The 58 beneficiaries answered the survey questionnaire through Google Forms while 15 answered the Google form during the house visit. Additionally, there are 8 out of 11 implementers of the DSWD educational assistance program from the SWAD office.

The initial section focuses on gathering the demographic background of the respondents consisting of the name of the school NVSU, PLTCI, or SMU, type of school whether public or private, type of student if working or non-working, licensed social worker or not, and the number of years in service. Subsequently, the questionnaire delves into the challenges in the implementation of the program faced by recipients and the implementers of DSWD educational assistance in terms of the process with six questions and the distribution with five questions, utilizing a Likert scale ranging from one (Disagree) to four (Highly Agree). Additionally, open-ended questions were incorporated to elicit insightful information from the respondents. Some questions indicated were "What are recommendations to solve the challenges in the implementation of the DSWD educational assistance program".

Results and Discussion

Section 1. This section presents the data gathered about the profile of the respondents consisting of the name of the school, type of school, and type of student. Additionally, the profile of the implementers consists of the number of years in service and license status.

A. Recipients

Out of 73 recipients 48 (65.75%) study at Nueva Vizcaya State University, 15 (20.55%) studied at PLT College Inc., and 10 (13.70%) study at Saint Mary's University. This implies that most of the recipients are from the public school Nueva Vizcaya State University. This shows there is more in need within this institution than the private school because of the high tuition, wherein they apply for educational assistance from DSWD to lessen their financial problems. Most recipients are non-working with 59 (80.33%) indicating they are more focused on academics. Despite the small number of Working students, 14 (19.18%) of the population need an extra income for their daily necessities. Furthermore, the distribution of public and private institutions indicates a preference for higher accessibility to public education within this group.

B. Implementers

The eight implementers were categorized into two groups based on their "Number of Years in Service" and "License Status." The average length of service is 2 years and 8 months, reflecting an intermediate level of expertise among the implementers. The service duration ranges from a minimum of nine months to a maximum of eight years, indicating variability in experience levels. The majority of the implementers are licensed social workers, with 6 (75%) holding licenses and 2 (25%) not holding licenses. According to Dawn Apgar (2019), consequently, the predominance of licensed social workers within the group suggests a high overall level of professional accreditation. Nevertheless, the presence of unlicensed social workers does not necessarily denote a deficiency in competence but rather indicates a different phase in their professional development.

Section 2. Level of Difficulty experienced in the implementation of the DSWD educational assistance program.

A. Recipients

Level of difficulty experienced in terms of Processing the Program Requirements

The overall mean rating is 1.50, suggesting that respondents generally do not find the process particularly difficult or problematic, as indicated by the qualitative description of "Very Low." Specifically, the validation of requirements, which took considerable time, had the highest mean score of 1.88. In contrast, the issue of inappropriate requirements received the lowest mean score of 1.23. According to Asuncion and Tullao Jr. (2018), there are still some issues that need to be resolved, like the requirement for proper management to carry out the program.

Level of Difficulty experienced in terms of the Distribution of Educational Assistance

The overall mean rating is 1.47, placing it in the "very low" category; this may suggest that most recipients do not view these problems as significant. The distribution of educational assistance sometimes experiences delays, receiving the highest mean score of 1.63. In contrast, the issue of the assistance distribution location being difficult to access has the lowest mean score of 1.29. Despite the overall disagreement with the severity of these issues, the mean rating's proximity to the "low" level (1.50) indicates that a notable portion of respondents perceive moderate difficulties.

According to Teshome et al. (2020), the problem of service delivery is growing into a worldwide issue that necessitates constant reform to fit the unstable environment and shifting client needs. In contrast to the private sector, public sector organizations "need to cater to the needs" of the entire community regardless of their background and socioeconomic class. Clients expect the provision of efficient and high-quality services.

Section 3. Significant difference in the level of difficulty experienced in the implementation of the DSWD educational assistance program when grouped according to their profile.

A. Recipients

1. Name of School

Significant Difference in the Level of Difficulty Experienced when Grouped According to the Name of the School

The overall responses for both challenges tend towards disagreement, with most respondents indicating they do not face significant challenges. SMU's respondents showed slightly higher mean scores, indicating a moderate agreement, particularly for "Processing the Program Requirements." However, the Kruskal-Wallis test results indicate no statistically significant differences in the perceptions of these challenges among the three schools. The results then accept the hypothesis that the challenges of the recipients have no significant difference when grouped according to the name of the school. This suggests that a student's name of school does not influence their challenges.

According to Baum (2020), students from both public and private institutions report similar levels of frustration with administrative processes such as program requirement processing and financial aid claims. The study suggests that despite differences in institutional governance and resources, students across the board encounter comparable difficulties. So, it can be implied that college students experienced different challenges in processing and claiming educational assistance regardless of their school's name.

2. Type of school (Public or Private)

Significant Difference in the Level of Difficulty Experienced When Grouped according to Type of School

Both students from public and private schools have a low level of difficulty in encountering the challenges with processing program requirements. However, there is a difference in perceptions of the distribution of educational assistance: public school students face challenges, while private school students experience low levels of difficulty. The p-value from the analysis is greater than the significance level of 0.05, leading us to accept the null hypothesis. This suggests that, despite the differences in individual perceptions, the overall challenges experienced by students do not differ significantly when grouped by the type of school.

Evans and Nguyen (2019) emphasize that the bureaucratic hurdles in processing financial aid are a widespread issue across different types of institutions. Students frequently face delays, unclear guidelines, and administrative inefficiencies when accessing financial assistance, regardless of whether they attend public or private schools.

3. Type of Student (Working or Non-working)

Significant Difference in the Level of Difficulty of the Recipients when grouped according to Type of Student

Based on the results, working students reported a "low" level of difficulty for both challenges, with mean scores of 1.83 for processing program requirements and 1.65 for distribution of educational assistance. In contrast, non-working students generally had "very low" scores with the significance of these challenges, with mean scores of 1.42 and 1.43, respectively. The Mann-Whitney test results indicate statistically significant differences between the two groups. The p-values for both challenges are below the significance level of 0.05 ($p = 0.001$ for processing program requirements and $p = 0.027$ for distribution of educational assistance), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that working students experience more significant challenges compared to non-working students.

Baja (2024) also highlights that students who work long hours encounter more substantial obstacles in managing time, balancing work and academic responsibilities, and coping with the stress of multiple commitments.

B. Implementers

1. Number of years in service

Significant Difference in the level of difficulty of the Implementers when grouped according to the Number of Years in Service

The results indicate that regardless of the number of years of service, both groups disagree that they face significant challenges in both Processing the Program Requirements and Distribution of Educational Assistance. The lack of variation in the mean scores and the non-significant results from the Mann-Whitney U test suggest that there is no significant difference in the challenges of the implementers when grouped according to the number of Years in Service which means, the hypothesis was accepted.

It is implied that the number of years in service does not affect the perception of these challenges. The responses across both categories are uniform, indicating no difference in the experience between the two groups or the number of years doesn't affect the challenges of implementers. As Mendoza, Luigi et al. (2022) stated, years of service do not affect their performance and their level of difficulty in the challenges that they have encountered.

2. Licensed or Not Licensed

Significant Difference in the Level of Difficulty of the Implementers When Grouped according to License Status

In processing the program requirements: both licensed and non-licensed respondents consistently indicate that there is very low level of difficulty in processing program requirements. Similar to the distribution of educational assistance, both groups also have very low level of difficulty in the distribution of educational assistance. The results of the Mann-Whitney test indicate no significant difference in the Challenges of the Implementers when grouped according to License Status, which means that the hypothesis was accepted.

The results suggest that license status does not significantly influence the perception of challenges related to processing program requirements and the distribution of educational assistance. Moreover, Säfström M. and Löfkvist U. (2024) stated that implementation processes are challenging for employees. The impact that organizational change has on the work environment should be considered. So, it means that other factors influence the challenges faced by implementers and do not lie within the licensed status issue, which implies that the licensed status of a worker does not affect the challenges of implementers or workers in the implementation of educational assistance.

Section 4. Recommendations to solve the challenges in the implementation of the DSWD educational assistance program.**A. Recipients**

Recommendations by the Recipients in Solving the Challenges in the Implementation of the DSWD Educational Assistance

Theme 1: Organizational Process

41.10% of the 73 total respondents recommended that taking additional measures would solve the challenges of the recipients within the said program. This theme emphasizes the recommendations about the overall implementation of the DSWD educational assistance, wherein an increase in its manpower should be provided for an easier, faster, and more systematic process. Furthermore, building collaborative efforts with schools will enhance the time allotted to secure, process, and validate requirements. A respondent also raised a recommendation in solving a challenge in terms of the time convenient to the class schedule of the student recipients.

The study of Peretomode and Ikoya (2019), emphasized that harnessing manpower also known as Human Resource Planning (HRP) is an important element in achieving the goals of a certain organization. Significantly, manpower management involves the right number of people or quantity needed in the execution of something to achieve a goal. Ozkeser (2019) also asserted that scientific approaches in human resources management (HRM) related to human resource planning or manpower improvement can greatly enhance the effectiveness of an organizational structure. This claim supports the idea that other issues rising during the implementation of the DSWD educational assistance may be reduced if the organization allocates more workforce.

Theme 2: Participation of Recipients

From the 73 total respondents, 10.90% concluded that an improvement on the participation of the recipients should also be observed, which they consider as a hindering factor for an easier implementation process of the DSWD educational assistance.

The theme highlights that the recipients should have an active involvement in the implementation such as the need to complete all needed requirements during submission to avoid a lengthy process. Recipients should also take part in improving such programs. The participation of recipients denotes that the recipients' input can be a significant part of both the implementation and further improvements of the program. As mentioned in the study of Lamponen and Aarnio (2024), a practitioner conducting an assessment for a certain situation must be formulated from the information provided at hand. In the context of the DSWD educational assistance program, recipients are encouraged to pass all needed requirements for assessment whereas, this is the very first process of the program in identifying its beneficiaries.

Theme 3: Information Dissemination

The data gathered shows that 5.48% of the 73 total respondents recommended an improvement with regard to the information dissemination of the DSWD educational assistance. Information dissemination emphasizes the announcement of the availability of educational assistance so that all potential beneficiaries can be informed and prepared. Moreover, implementers are also suggested to conduct outreach methods to inform potential beneficiaries about the educational assistance. A clearer and more definite list of requirements must also be included for recipients to be prepared and to avoid lacking in requirements. This theme points out that a timely announcement about the availability of the DSWD educational assistance including the needed details about the requirements should be easily accessible to all possible beneficiaries.

Findings of a related study, where governments were recommended to provide fair, transparent, timely, and accurate information dissemination to promote trust from the public also agree with this claim (Chen et al., 2024).

B. Implementers

Recommendations by the Implementers in Solving the Challenges in the Implementation of the DSWD Educational Assistance

Theme 1: Cooperation of Recipients

The table presented that 75% of the 8 total respondents recommended that the cooperation of recipients must be observed as it also affects the challenges in the implementation of the DSWD educational assistance. This theme reveals additional effort from the recipients as well to implement the educational assistance successfully. Such as their full compliance with the needed requirements, cooperation in the processes, and discipline to avoid disruptions in the middle of the processes.

These findings imply that recipients also cover a responsibility within the program's processes up to its implementation. Recipients need to contribute a collaborative effort with the implementers to deliver the objectives of the DSWD educational assistance program successfully. The study of Grieco and Bripi (2022) mentioned that the involvement of beneficiaries may provide support in achieving the charity's objectives and the possibility of shielding these objectives from complications.

Theme 2: Enhancement of Manpower

A significant theme represented by 12.5% of the total respondents of the implementers recommended that there is a need for an enhancement of the manpower within the implementation of the DSWD educational assistance. This theme indicates that the struggle with lack of manpower is also a challenge in implementing the said program which is highly needed for a faster process to avoid delays and to guarantee a more systematic execution of the educational assistance program. Following this is a reassuring outcome that the program will serve its purpose.

In exploring the shortage of academic staff in higher institutions of learning in Nigeria, Jacob and Garba (2021) concluded that negative impacts on the quality of teaching and overcrowding are considered the result of a shortage of academic staff within the said institution. The DSWD educational assistance program encounters challenges due to a lack of manpower as well and as recommended by Jacob and Garba (2024) in their study, increasing the number of staff is one solution to consider.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the challenges in implementing the DSWD educational assistance program, focusing on the difficulties encountered in processing requirements and distributing assistance to provide a basis for program enhancement. The findings revealed no significant differences in the level of difficulty faced by recipients, regardless of school name, type of school, or type of student. Similarly, implementers experienced comparable challenges in processing requirements and distributing assistance, irrespective of their years of service or whether they were licensed or non-licensed social workers.

However, the qualitative analysis uncovered valuable themes for improvement. Among recipients, the primary challenges were categorized into three themes: Organizational Process (41.10%), Participation of Recipients (10.96%), and Information Dissemination (5.48%). For implementers, key themes included the need for improved Cooperation of Recipients (75%) and Enhancement of Manpower (12.5%). While the challenges identified were generally manageable,

these findings highlight areas where targeted interventions could streamline program operations and improve the overall experience for both recipients and implementers. For the limitations of this study, future researchers may utilize a more qualitative approach for respondents to state concerns and issues within the program freely.

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